

THE PROBLEM ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS OF CREATIVE THINKING IN EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya: ijodiylik in the process of education is considered important. Teachers with lesson namsd classes in the process of the new methods is considered important. Activities with descriptions of the scientific basis for effective results.

Keywords: personality, social factors, the thought process, theoretical concepts, research, significance, impact methods, teaching activities

The person constantly in the development of society in the development of scientific, theoretical and practical analysis are presented. A psychologist, a scientist developed the theory of personality development, representing the essence of shoes by v. v. also common. The introduction of this theory by primary-grade students with the goal to create favorable conditions for the development of scientific understanding will promote compliance. Accordingly, the system of theoretical concepts mastered in the process of education, students should go. This process ensures the transition from private to general knowledge.

The essence of the theory of general intellectual development of the person and determines the number of those in education process aimed at the same goal can be problematic, problematic technology, the importance of education is highly valued. Zankov, I. v. and m. a. psychologist Matyushkinlar this reason scientists in the research carried out by a problematic of opportunities in the process of education lesson proper, it is necessary to order it with special attention paid to effective use.

Developing teaching and training emphasis is given to the psychological aspects of its structural elements technology access issues. Stressed education as the success of a number of psychological factors, in particular, depends on the relationship of the student to read. Turn the attention of the student in relationship, feelings, interests, and keeps it in a way that appears.

The process of education is, above all, requires you to know to feed on the attention of students. In the lesson visual aids, the use of computer tools in education ixtiyorsiz attention they bring technical and buyers. The tasks in the teacher's lesson to the condition not arising of work, but readers also to the perception of how they were prepared for the observation that o'rganiladigan material. Readers carefully during the course varies. For this reason carefully and keep in mind that this qonuniyat students in the education process to attract the main aspects of the material, repeat them need to pay attention to.

One of the factors that enhance the effects of teachers in the teaching process – his voice, the features are listed that are specific to him. The voice of the teacher to be pretty full of himself and get paid to jarangdor ensures that the attention of students. How to determine the sensitivity of his voice is the voice of the teacher at the level of the strong, and know that shirada be pleasant as well as efficient to use in situations like this the voice of the required features should get. The teachers who felt that there are certain gaps in his voice should try to eliminate them. To do this technique and use it to improve the voice consistent, constant exercise will be required to go on to do. After all, exercise will not be made thoroughly one or two times with the sound properties.

The voice of the teacher should take time to reflect at the following features: 1) let jarangdor (the purity of sound and the brightness of tembr); 2) a wide range of (voice low and far the top most level); 3) havodorlik (free when delivered to be able eshituvchanlikka good); 4) compact mobility; 5) durability (long to have the ability to work); 6) adapted (dynamics, tembr); 7) compared to the stability

against noise (noise which interfere with the changing of tembr be); 8) suggetsivlik (voice of xayajon and represent that through this, how to say the word, in spite of the audience to influence the behavior of the feature).

All of these workers who are looking for specific requires. During my lessons, teachers are creative, to be aware of the latest achievements of science to know of updates is considered important.

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